

G along with further quantities of substances D and F.

TABLE 1—SUBSTANCES ISOLATED FROM *B. grandiflora*

Sl. No.	Compounds	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield† percentage
1.	Substance A (<i>n</i> -Hentriacontane)	C ₃₁ H ₆₄	64	0.141
2.	Substance B (<i>n</i> -Triacontane)	C ₃₂ H ₆₆	66	0.026
3.	Substance C (Palmitic acid)	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	61	0.013
4.	Substance D (β -sitosterol)	C ₂₇ H ₅₀ O	135	0.050
5.	Substance E (Linoleic acid)	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	202(BP)*	0.032
6.	Substance F (Ursolic acid)	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ O ₆	283	0.108
7.	Substance G (β -sitosterol- β -D-glucopyranoside)	C ₅₃ H ₁₀₀ O ₆	301(d)	0.031

† Based on the weight of dry plant material

* Yellowish viscous liquid

Characterisation of the substances A-G was based on physical data (uv, ir, nmr and mass spectra) and formation of acetyl and methyl ester derivatives, wherever possible.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. S. K. Upadhyaya, M. S. College, Saharanpur for collection and identification of the plant and to Dr. R. S. Kapil, CDRI, Lucknow for authentic samples and for spectra of the substances. One of the authors (M. P. S.) is thankful to UGC for financial assistance.

References

1. The Wealth of India, Raw Materials, C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1950, 1, 166.
2. A. F. KRASSE, E. K. WEISS and I. REICHSTEIN, *Pharm. Acta Helva.*, 1964, 39, 168.
3. A. F. KRASSE and E. K. WEISS, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1963, 46, 1691.
4. N. G. BISSERT, *Ann. begr.*, 1957, 2, 193.

Occurrence of 2,7-Dihydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxy-9,10-dihydrophenanthrene in *Coelogyne ovalis*, A High Altitude Himalayan Orchid: Application of C-13 NMR Spectroscopy in Structure Elucidation

P. L. MAJUMDER* and (MISS) SWAPNA LAHA

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 1 November 1980, revised 8 April 1981, accepted 15 July 1981

THE isolation of physiologically active alkaloids like dendrobine and a number of its structural analogues from the orchid *Dendrobium nobile*^{1,2} prompted us to undertake systematic chemical investigation of a series of high altitude Himalayan orchids. In this communication we report the

characterisation of the title compound (1a) isolated from one of these orchids, *Coelogyne ovalis*.

Air-dried powdered whole plant of *C. ovalis* (1 kg) was exhaustively extracted with chloroform in a soxhlet apparatus. The concentrated chloroform extract was chromatographed over silica gel. The petrol-ethylacetate (5:1) eluate afforded a crude phenolic mass which was taken in ether and extracted with 1N NaOH solution. The aqueous alkaline solution was acidified with HCl in the cold and the liberated solid was extracted with ether, dried and the solvent removed. The residue on repeated chromatography over silica gel gave a pure compound, C₁₇H₁₈O₅ (M⁺302), m.p. 109°, crystallised from petrol-benzene mixture. With Ac₂O and pyridine it formed a diacetyl derivative, C₂₁H₂₂O₇ (M⁺386), m.p. 107°. The physical constants and the spectral data (uv, ir, pmr and mass) of the coelogyne-phenol and its diacetate compare excellently with those reported³ for 1a isolated from the heart-wood of *Combretum psidioides* and its diacetyl derivative (1b) respectively. Since a direct comparison was not possible due to non-availability of authentic samples of 1a and 1b, further evidence was sought to confirm the structure

1a : R=H, 1b : R=Ac

of the coelogyne-phenol. The compound was heated in a sealed tube filled with nitrogen, with D₂O/KOBU⁴ for 70 hr. The ¹H-nmr spectrum of the product was identical with that of the parent compound except that the integrated areas of the aromatic proton signals at δ 6.55 (H-1) and 6.70 (H-8) were reduced to about 65% and 50% respectively, contrary to complete disappearance of these signals as reported³ earlier for 1a. The MS of the reaction mixture showed molecular ions at m/e 302 and 304. This observation is in conformity with the structure 1a for coelogyne-phenol.

Further confirmation of the structure of the compound was made by ¹³C-nmr spectral analysis of its diacetyl derivative. The carbon shifts and the degree of protonation of the carbons were determined by the proton-noise decoupled (NDC) and the single frequency off-resonance (SFORD) spectra, respectively of 1b. Excepting C-3, C-4 and C-5, the carbon shifts (the carbon shifts were measured using the relationship ⁵TMS = ⁵CDCl₃ + 76.9 ppm

and those having close values as marked with asterisk are interchangeable) of 1b as portrayed in its structure are in good agreement with the values calculated by using the known additivity parameters of the functional groups on the reported carbon shifts of the 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene⁴. The observed downfield shift of C-3 and C-4 by ~9 ppm is characteristic⁵ of adjacent aromatic carbons bearing oxygen functions. The downfield shift of C-5 by ~9 ppm may be attributed to the proximity of the C-4 methoxyl group. This constitutes the first report of the application of ¹³C-nmr spectroscopy in the structure elucidation of the naturally occurring 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivative and the diagnostic features that are revealed may be used for future structural studies of this group of natural products.

Acknowledgement

We thank Dr. B. C. Das, Institut de Chimie des Substances Naturelles, Gif-sur-Yvette, France for the mass spectra and Professor E. Wenkert, Rice University, U.S.A. for the ¹³C-nmr spectra. (S.L.) is thankful to U.G.C., India for financial assistance.

References

- (a) Y. HIRATA and S. YAMAMURA, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1964, 79.
- (b) Y. INUBUSHI, Y. SASAKI, Y. TSUDA, B. YASUI, T. KONITA, J. MATSUMOTO, E. KATARAO and J. NAKANO, *Tetrahedron*, 1964, 20, 2007.
- (c) Y. INUBUSHI, Y. SASAKI, Y. TSUDA and J. NAKANO, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, 1519.
- (d) T. ONAKA, S. KAMATA, T. MAEDA, Y. KAWAZOE, N. NATSUME, T. OKAMOTO, F. UCHIMARU and M. SHIMIZU, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1964, 12, 506.
- (a) K. YAMADA, M. SUZUKI, Y. HAWAKAWA, K. AOKI, H. NAKAMURA, H. NAGASE and Y. HIRATA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 94, 8278.
- (b) Y. INUBUSHI, T. KIKUCHI, T. IBUKA, K. TANAKA, I. SAJI and K. TOKANE, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1974, 22, 349.
- R. M. LETCHER and L. R. M. NHAMO, *J. Chem. Soc. (Perkin I)*, 1972, 2941.
- J. B. STOTHERS, "C-13 NMR Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1972.
- E. WENKERT, H. E. GOTTLIEB, O. R. GOTTLIEB, M. O. DAS PEREIRA and M. D. FORMIGA, *Phytochemistry*, 1976, 15, 1547.

O-(*N*- α -Pyrrolideneimino)Benzene Sulphonic Acid as an Analytical Reagent for Estimation of V(V)

C. P. GUPTA, K. G. SHARMA and R. K. MEHTA
Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur,
Jodhpur-342 001

Manuscript received 27 October 1980, revised 1 June 1981,
accepted 15 July 1981

A number of organic reagents^{1,2} have been suggested for gravimetric estimation of vanadium(V). The present work is undertaken with the aim to introduce a new reagent, *o*-(*N*- α -Pyrrolideneimino)-benzene sulphonic acid (H_2PB), for gravimetric

estimation of vanadium(V). The vanadium(V)-complex is insoluble in water and can form the basis of a quantitative separation procedure. H_2PB , prepared by the method already reported^{3,4}, (m.p. 172°) gives a rose red precipitate with V(V) in the pH range 3.2-4.0.

Experimental

1% ethanolic solution of H_2PB was used as the reagent. VO_2NO_3 was standardised gravimetrically⁵. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Determination of vanadium(V): An aliquot of the vanadium solution [25 to 55 mg of V(V)] was diluted to about 125 ml with distilled water, pH was adjusted between 3.2-4.0 with $HClO_4$ and NH_4OH and heated at 40°-50°. The reagent solution was added gradually with stirring till precipitation completed. It was heated on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr and allowed to stand for 2-3 hrs when a granular precipitate formed. It was filtered through a weighed sintered-glass crucible (porosity 4), washed successively with warm water and 10% alcohol until free from the reagent. The complex was dried to a constant weight at 100-110° in a vacuum desiccator, cooled and weighed as $[VO_2 \cdot (C_{11}H_8N_2SO_3)(H_2O)]$. The operation was repeated several times using different quantities of V(V) solutions and results obtained are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM

Wt. of complex (mg)	Vanadium (mg)		Error %
	Calcd.	Found	
181.6	26.53	26.45	-0.30
241.0	35.21	35.14	-0.19
279.4	40.82	40.92	+0.24
306.5	44.78	44.69	-0.20
340.7	49.78	49.89	+0.22

The complex was soluble in concentrated mineral acids, alkalis, dioxan and DMF.

The thermogravimetric analysis of the precipitate indicated a weight loss at 120°-180° corresponding to a water molecule. On further heating a gradual loss in weight due to slow decomposition of the complex was observed. On heating between 380-440°, a sudden loss in weight was recorded and V_2O_5 obtained as the end product.

Effect of foreign ions: In order to assess possible analytical applications of the reagent effect of some ions which often accompanied vanadium was studied.

The interference due to salts of foreign ions was removed in most of the cases by working at controlled pH. In V(V) determination in the pH range 3.2-4.0, anions like CH_3COO^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} did not interfere.

For 0.1 mg of V(V) solution, the tolerance limit was 25 mg for Be(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Cr(II), Cd(II), Zn(II); 10-15 mg for U(VI), Zr(IV), Th(IV) and Sc(III) and 5 mg for Pt(IV). The Fe(III), Ni(II)